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Innovative battery materials: it's all about chemistry!

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The energy crisis and renewable energy

Energy prices are dominated by our dependence on fossil fuels.

We are very vulnerable to geopolitical issues.

We must make efficient use of renewable energy sources.

Which roll can we play as chemists?

The energy crisis and renewable energy

Photovoltaics

Wind

Intermittent renewable energy must be stored efficiently.

- P2X
 - Water splitting
 - CCU
- Batteries

The energy crisis and renewable energy

The DESINe group

- Synthesis and characterization of inorganic materials
- More than a decade of experience with research on battery materials
- Lithium-ion, sodium-ion, Li-S

Use chemistry for improved:

- ✓ Sustainability
- ✓ Durability
- ✓ Cost-efficiency
- ✓ Energy density
- ✓ Etc.

How does a battery work?

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Typically contains cobalt

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Reacts with the liquid electrolyte, causing a drop in capacity

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The cathode typically contains cobalt

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- The cathode is typically a layered oxide
- Layered LiCoO_2 has dominated the market for the past 20 years

Chemical synthesis allows us to improve the material:

- Reduction of the Co amount
 - ✓ Reduced toxicity
 - ✓ Improved sustainability
- Incorporation of an excess of lithium
 - ✓ High energy density

Li Ni Mn

The cathode typically contains cobalt

Spray pyrolysis was used for the synthesis of $\text{Li}_{1.1}\text{Ni}_{0.35}\text{Mn}_{0.55}\text{O}_2$ as Co-free, Li-rich layered oxide

The cathode reacts with the electrolyte

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Coating the active material cores with a protective and conductive shell
 TiO_x shells on layered $\text{LiNi}_{0.6}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$

The cathode reacts with the electrolyte

Coating the active material cores with a protective shell

TiO_x shells on layered LiNi_{0.6}Mn_{0.2}Co_{0.2}O₂

**The anode has a low electrochemical
stability**

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The electrolyte is flammable and leaks

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The electrolyte is flammable and leaks

Deep eutectic solvents (DESs): mixture of acid/bases with melting point below that of individual components

Electrolytes for alkali ion batteries

Conventional

Low vapor pressure	X
Non-flammable	X
Ease of preparation	✓
Cost-effective	✓

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Electrolytes for alkali ion batteries

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Non-flammable	X	✓
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The electrolyte is flammable and leaks

1.52 m

3.42 m

5.86 m

The electrolyte is flammable and leaks

Solid electrolytes

- ✓ No leakage
- ✓ Increased energy density

Silica

Polymer

Conclusion

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Batteries can lead us to a bright future...

..but we need bright chemists to pave the way!

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The complete DESINe group
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I WANT YOU
FOR DESINe
ARMY

